

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

ON THE CAUSALITY OF BEHAVIOR IN THE MICROCOSM

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Abstract

The paper addresses the issue of causal behavior of micro-world objects by studying the electron that exists in free and bound states. In doing so, tasks involving radiation of a hydrogen-like atom and scattering are tackled. The methods of integer number theory are employed to solve these tasks. The feasibility of applying such a solution method is justified through the introduction of a hypothesis into physics, known as the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities. Quantum states of the electron in a hydrogen atom result from the necessity to have a common measure for energy, momentum, and angular momentum of the electron in its ground and any other excited state. This is how Bohr's quantum hypothesis receives a physical justification and the physical foundations of the cause-and-effect relationship between any states of quantum systems that are realized in nature during the interaction of such systems become clear. The possible physical nature of the indefinite initial state of a quantum object is discussed even before its entry into interaction, and then the physical reason for indeterminism in describing the World by quantum physics becomes clear. From the principle of commensurability, the application of which allows one to correctly solve physical problems, it follows that at the birth of the World, in which we reside, morality was laid down as the highest principle of distribution of goods, which is preserved absolutely.

Keywords: causality in physics, principle of commensurability of conserved quantities, integer theory, spectral series of hydrogen-like atom, problem of scattering

1. Introduction

With the advent of quantum mechanics, ideas about the world in which we live have changed significantly. The results of the interaction between physical objects on the scale of the microcosm have a probabilistic nature. However, it is quite natural to want to understand the true, namely physical reasons for such a probabilistic behavior of the entities of the microworld. W. Heisenberg very deeply formulates the description of the process of interaction in the microworld. In [1], he writes that the interaction process can be divided into three stages:

- a) the initial experimental situation is represented as a certain probability function
- b) the change of this function is established (with the help of a computing apparatus)
- c) a new measurement is made, and the expected result is then determined from the probability function.

Thus, we see that when describing the interaction by quantum physics, already at the very beginning, even before the micro-object enters into the interaction, its state is probabilistic. The "Copenhagen school" of the interpretation of quantum mechanics associates such an initial uncertainty with the need to measure the initial state of a physical object before it enters into an interaction in order to know and, accordingly, *set its initial state* to describe its further behavior during the interaction itself. In this case, no matter what device for measuring the initial state of a quantum object is invented, the uncertainty of the initial state still cannot be less than the one that follows from the well-known Heisenberg uncertainty relation: $\Delta p_x \Delta x > h$. But it is important to realize that the resulting uncertainty relation is a mathematical phenomenon. It must be admitted that there is no other *physical explanation* (interpretation)

of the *mathematical phenomenon* of the uncertainty relation, except for the "Copenhagen interpretation". But we emphasize once again that uncertainty itself is inherent in a naturally existing method of describing physical reality and *does not require specification of any mechanism for the interaction of particles with a measuring device* (that is, it is a mathematical phenomenon) and this was convincingly shown, in particular, also by Krainov [2]. Then what is the physical reason (physical nature) of the uncertainty of the state of a quantum object *before it enters into interaction*?

It is clear that if we somehow introduce uncertainty into the initial state of a quantum object, then this will inevitably lead to the uncertainty of its final state, that is to the probabilistic result of the experiment, and hence to the indeterministic (in the classical sense) behavior of the object. Is there an alternative to the "Copenhagen interpretation" of the mandatory uncertainty of the state of a quantum object before it enters into an interaction? It is necessary to find out the possible physical reason for such a mandatory uncertainty (a reason that would be different from the fact that it is necessary *to make a measurement* before the interaction). If we are now able to calculate the interaction process using existing mathematical methods and the results of such calculations are confirmed by experiment, is this enough to answer the question: why does this apparatus correctly describe the experiment? Yes, we know how the World works and we can describe it (calculate, predict it), but we do not know *why* it is arranged this way.

In other words, we also do not have an answer to the question: why does Nature quantize states, why does Nature have "allowed" and "forbidden" states of the atom, that is what is *at the basis* of Bohr's quantum hypothesis? Now it is considered sufficient that Bohr's

hypothesis is confirmed both by the data of numerous physical experiments and by calculations using the modern apparatus of quantum mechanics. But it is clear that there must be some *physical causes* of quantum states in Nature, because there is no doubt that these states existed not only before the Bohr hypothesis and the Schrödinger equations, but long before the appearance of homo sapiens on Earth.

In this work, we will seek answers to these formulated questions.

2. Principle of commensurability of conserved quantities

Since within the existing methods of knowledge of physical reality, there is no answer to the questions formulated above, they must be sought in a different paradigm. We propose introducing a new principle - *the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities*, which is formulated as follows:

when physical objects interact, the conserved quantities (such as energy, momentum, etc.) are redistributed between the objects in such a way that the values of similar conserved quantities have a common measure for all participants of the interaction, both before and after the interaction, for all conserved quantities that are relevant to this interaction.

As is known from higher mathematics, a common measure for two quantities a and b (or a greater number of quantities) will always take place if their ratio, a/b , is expressed by a rational number. In this case, both quantities are commensurable and can be expressed as an integer number of units of measure (it is very important that *each* of the quantities can also be a unit of measure, that is, *it can be used to measure any other* of the set of commensurable quantities). A classic example of two incommensurable quantities is the diagonal and the side of a square. They cannot be measured with the same "meter", respectively, the diagonal cannot be measured with the help of a side. The ancient Greeks knew this, and due to the fact that such a simple geometric figure could not be described using integers (there is no common measure, therefore these quantities cannot be expressed in integers), the Pythagorean school of integers perished. But if the conserved physical quantities are commensurable, then we can solve the problems of interaction, for example, of physical objects using the methods of the theory of integers.

In [3], a detailed description of the solution of the problem of radiation of a hydrogen-like atom is given using the principle of commensurability. All spectral series of atomic radiation have been obtained. All previously established "magic" numbers that characterize transitions between the states of an atom acquire a clear physical meaning: the "allowed" states of an electron in an atom are those states that have a common measure with the ground state in three conserved quantities (in this particular case, in three) are the energy, momentum, and angular momentum. Bohr's quantum hypothesis ceases to be mysterious - all allowed states of the electron (that is, those that can only be realized in Nature for a given system) must be commensurate in terms of conserved values with the ground state.

The result obtained in [3] is interpreted from the point of view of physics as follows. When physical objects interact, quantities that are absolutely conserved (energies, momenta, etc.) cannot be transferred from one object to another in such a way that the initial value of the conserved quantity could not be measured using the transferred part. These quantities must be transferred from one object to another *as an integer value of units of the common measure of interacting objects*, because the conserved quantity does not disappear anywhere and does not appear from nothing. The absolute value of a unit of measure can, of course, be expressed by an irrational number, because irrational numbers occupy an exact place on the number axis (see, for example [4]), but the transfer of a conserved value from one physical object to another can be carried out only by an integer number of units general measure. And only such (exclusively such) interactions are realized in the experiment, that is in Nature (this fact was established when making calculations using the principle of commensurability). In other words, the very concept of "quantization" is a *consequence* of the need for commensurability.

Naturally, the question arises: what is the unit of measure, what is its absolute value for each conserved quantity?

For the bound states of an electron, the values of units of measure can be determined - *this is the absolute value of the conserved quantities for the ground state of the electron*. If the units of measure for all conserved quantities that are relevant to a given interaction are established, then there is a completely clear physical reason that governs the allowed states of the system (that is those states that are realized in Nature) - these are states that have a common measure with the ground state over all conserved quantities that are relevant to the given state.

Now we can claim that we understand the physical nature (cause) of the "allowed" states of the atom (and not Bohr's hypothesis to consider the cause of these states or the cause to consider the results of solving the Schrödinger equations), and therefore we understand the causal relationship between the initial and any other possible state of the system, which is capable (that is only it and *no other*) to be realized in Nature. Bohr's quantum conditions are a *consequence* of the need to fulfill the commensurability of the quantum states of systems. This causal behavior of a quantum system can be called deterministic.

The investigated allowed states using the principle of commensurability for the simplest case of the interaction of two elementary particles (proton and electron) nevertheless make it possible to understand the physical causes that govern the structuring of multielectron atoms, and any more complex developing structures, up to the most complex, which demonstrates us wildlife. *Structuring in nature is governed by the need for commensurability of any new, more complex state with the previous, lower state in terms of all conserved values that are related to this structure.*

3. Scattering of an electron by a power center

The situation with the determination of the absolute value of the units of measure of conserved quantities for a free electron is much more complicated. Let us find out the possible physical nature of the units of measure for an unbound (free) electron. To do this, we first consider the problem of probe particle scattering on a power center with the simplest scattering potential in the form of a δ - function. The choice of this simplest type of interaction potential is due to the fact that the study of continuously changing potentials significantly complicates the interpretation of the physics of the obtained scattering results, and since in fact any potential can then be modeled by "steps" from a given element, it makes sense to study it. A detailed consideration of the problem of scattering at this potential was made in [5], but here we repeat some important stages of such a calculation for the integrity of the perception of the text and comment on the calculation results from the point of view of the goal set in this work.

Let us consider a probe particle elastic scattering on infinitely-heavy power centre in a laboratory frame of reference. Thus it is convenient that at probe particle scattering only dimensional orientation of its initial momentum changes, the absolute value of the momentum remains invariable.

To determine an angle of rotation of the vector of momentum of the probe particle with given initial p_0 after interaction with the power centre, it is sufficient to determine values of components along coordinates of this momentum after scattering in any of coordinate systems. We will use the Cartesian coordinate system for this purpose and place a scattering point in the centre of coordinate system.

To justify necessity of comparability of quantity of the momentum of the probe particle p_0 before interaction with its components on coordinates after the act

of scattering (that is, with p_x, p_y, p_z) we can suppose that if someone has tried to determine dimensional orientation of the momentum of the probe particle after scattering (and for this purpose, of course, it is necessary to know values of components along coordinates p_x, p_y, p_z), he could not measure p_0 , and its components along coordinates by same common measure if they were incommensurable. In the case when commensurability between them takes place, both the initial momentum and its components, measured by the same measure are integers. Thus, the number of admissible variants of scattering of the probe particle on power centre for one value of its energy E (that is, also its momentum p_0) is reduced to the solution of a mathematical problem of search of a number of decompositions of the whole quadrates of numbers on other three whole quadrates:

$$p_0^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2 \quad (1)$$

Some examples concerning determination of admissible variants of scattering of the probe particle on the power centre in angles $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ (that is, decompositions of the whole quadrates of numbers on other three whole quadrates) for the purpose of comparison of the obtained data on scattering with well-known from Newtonian and quantum mechanics have been solved numerically.

3.1 Technique of Numerical Experiment Performance

To illustrate the technique of numerical calculations performance, let us choose the arbitrary prime number $p_0^2 = 4999^2$. To determine the number of admissible scatterings of the probe particle with the value of its initial momentum $p_0 = 4999$, it is necessary to find all variants of decomposition of the quadrate of this number on other three whole quadrates. It has been done, results of the first 12 variants of decomposition are presented in Table I:

Table 1

Examples of decomposition of the quadrate of the number 4999² on other three whole quadrates (in cells first degrees of numbers, and not their quadrates are presented).

3	726	4946	3	1606	4734	3	1794	4666	3	2606	4266
14	99	4998	14	1386	4803	14	1773	4674	14	3078	3939
18	499	4974	18	669	4954	18	851	4926	18	1741	4686
18	1971	4594	18	2781	4154	18	3069	3946	18	3126	3901

It can be seen that in each table line "triples" of the numbers, which total of quadrates is equal 4999^2 are presented, since the very first triple: $3^2 + 726^2 + 4946^2 = 4999^2$, etc. One variant of decomposition of the number on three quadrates yields 48 points of a location of the vector of the momentum on the sphere of radius $p_0 = 4999$ if consider that each number from "triple" represents possible value of coordinate of the momentum of the probe particle.

For more detailed illustration of the technique of determination of the angle of deflection θ of the probe particle, for one of eight quadrants of the Cartesian coordinate system, the scheme of realization of two options (there are six of them in one quadrant) of the scattering corresponding to one variant of decomposition of number 4999^2 on three quadrates (let it be a decomposition example: $4999^2 = 86^2 + 2742^2 + 4179^2$) is presented in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. The scheme of realization of admissible variants of scattering of the probe particle on power centre for one decomposition of number on three quadrates: $4999^2 = 86^2 + 2742^2 + 4179^2$ in one of eight quadrants of the Cartesian system (one decomposition of a number into three squares results in six points of N scattering in one quadrant, if the numbers are interchanged)

So, the first variant of scattering for one decomposition of number: $4999^2 = 2742^2 + 4179^2 + 86^2 = p_{x1}^2 + p_{y1}^2 + p_{z1}^2$, we obtain a point of scattering N_1 with value of coordinates of the momentum $p_{x1} = 2742$, $p_{y1} = 4179$, $p_{z1} = 86$ on the sphere with radius $p = 4999$, value of the angle of deflection equally $\theta = \arcsin 86/4999 \approx 1^\circ$, (Fig. 1, point N_1).

The second variant of scattering (we rearrange places p_x , p_y): $4999^2 = 4179^2 + 2742^2 + 86^2 = p_{x2}^2 + p_{y2}^2 + p_{z2}^2$, we obtain a point of scattering N_2 on the sphere with radius $p = 4999$, value of the angle of deflection is also equal to $\theta = \arcsin 86/4999 \approx 1^\circ$ (Fig. 1, point N_2).

In such a manner evaluations for all obtained variants of decomposition of the number 4999^2 on three quadrates have been made and corresponding values of the angle of deflection of the probe particle θ are obtained. In total, number 4999^2 has 582 variants of decomposition on three quadrates, so $582 \times 48 = 27936$ points on the sphere with radius $p = 4999$.

After that, the discovered values of all angles of deflection of the probe particle θ have been averaged

over concrete discrete values of angles for construction of functional dependence. For example, to evaluate the number of hits of the corpuscle into the angle of 5° (actually, intensity of scattering I in this angle), the angle within the limits of $\Delta\theta_1 = 0^\circ - 5^\circ$ was chosen; further, the value of intensity of scattering in the following discrete angle equal to 10° was computed for all hits of a radius vector of a corpuscle over the angles range $\Delta\theta_2 = 5^\circ - 10^\circ$; further, for 15° , $\Delta\theta_3 = 10^\circ - 15^\circ$, etc., up to 90° , where $\Delta\theta_{17} = 85^\circ - 90^\circ$. The average numbers of hits computed by such method in discrete angles have been then divided on $\sin \Delta\theta_{aver}$, namely: $\sum I(0^\circ - 5^\circ) / \sin 2.5^\circ$, $\sum I(5^\circ - 10^\circ) / \sin 7.5^\circ$, etc. for the purpose to determine the value of density of scatterings in solid angle unity on a radius sphere p_0 . This is detailed in [5]. The data treated by such method allow construction of functional dependencies of averaged probabilities of scattering of the probe particle in the given angle within the angles of deflection $0^\circ - 90^\circ$.

The functional dependens, constructed on the basis of specified data processing are presented in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2. The number of hits $\sum I(\theta) / \sin \theta$ of the probe particle with value of momentum $p_0 = 4999$ in the solid angle θ at its scattering on power centre ($\sum I(\theta) / \sin \theta$ is proportional to the scattering cross-section)

So, the abscissa of the very first point on the drawing is equal to 2.5° , and the ordinate is equal to $\sum I(0^\circ - 5^\circ) / \sin 2.5^\circ$, for the second point the abscissa is 7.5° and ordinate is equal to $\sum I(5^\circ - 10^\circ) / \sin 7.5^\circ$, etc. Quantity $\sum I(\theta) / \sin \theta$, as it is already said, is proportional to the probe particle scattering cross-section in the given angle θ .

At rather rough averaging of the number of hits of the probe particle within discrete value of the angle of deflection with a step $\Delta\theta = 5^\circ$, small changes of value of a scattering cross-section are badly seen (too rough averaging), therefore for convenience the same curves, but in an expanded scale are presented in Fig. 2, namely, values of $\sum I(\theta) / \sin \theta$ are increased in 5 and 25 times.

3.2 Discussion of Scattering Results

From the data in Fig. 2, one can see the preferential deviation of the probe particle into angles of $47.50, 67.50, 82.50$ that is one can see the quantization of the scattering angles in the region of large angles of deflection of the particle.

In the region of angles of 27.50 and less, for this averaging, the preferential deflection of the particle is not seen, and the dependence of the scattering cross section on the angle θ passes to its form in classical physics. If the averaging angle $\Delta\theta$ is taken smaller, then a finer structure of scattering rings can be seen (detailed data are given in [5]). Such a fine structure of the distribution of a scattered particle over angles (that is, the distribution of scattering rings inside the preferential deflection angles) cannot be obtained by quantum mechanics methods by solving, for example, the corresponding wave equation (at least we do not know this). In addition, for very small particle energies, quantum

mechanics simply gives no dependence of the cross section on energy [6,7], while the above method can calculate the exact value of the cross section for any value of energy (when we say “exact” here, we mean, that the energy is given by a specific number, and the interaction potential has the form of a δ -function).

For very high energies of the probe particle, that is very large numbers, the distribution of scatter points will be uniform over the entire sphere. This is shown in the mathematical work [8], where the number of decompositions of the square of an integer into three other squares is considered with a continuous increase in the absolute value of the number. But the uniform distribution of scattering points on the sphere gives the classical result of the equiprobable distribution of the scattered particle to all angles without any quantization, that is leads to the well-known “Newtonian” equiprobable scattering. Thus, for a large value of the energy of the probe particle, the quantum result transforms into the classical one, which confirms the validity of the calculation model we have chosen.

The search for the absolute value of a unit of measure, with the help of which the fixed energy of a probe particle is expressed by the number of units of this measure, that is can be expressed by some integer, is important because the same value of the energy of a probe particle can be expressed by a different integer number of units of measure, depending on the absolute value of the unit of measure. A fundamental question arises: *what is the unit of measure for a free particle that is scattered by some center of power?* To do this, consider the scheme of scattering on a continuously changing interaction potential, as, for example, shown in Fig. 3.

Let us set up the following experiment (this scheme is partly discussed in [9]): under real, laboratory conditions, we fix some charged particle N surrounded by a power field (for example, a charged

ball on a fixed rod). Let us place a source r_A of charged probe particles M at some distance from the power center. Let the interaction potential φ change from the power center to the source as shown in Fig.3.

FIG.3 Scheme of interaction of the probe particle M in the field φ of the power center N . r_A is the location point of the source of probe particles

As the stationary field φ of the power center N decreases, its value will eventually reach the level of the average "noise" of fields from all entities of the Universe (at the point r_{min} in Fig. 3). Let the probe particle receive at the point r_A from the power source some energy, which is given by the experimenter and moves with momentum P in the direction of the power center in stochastic fields E_{stoch} (of course, not only electromagnetic, but of a different nature). When moving towards the power center, the particle will also feel the influence of the stationary field φ of the power center, but only as one component of the entire quantity of field sources.

It is obvious that a particle that has left the source at the point r_A and moves in the "noisy" field of the medium to the power center N acquires an uncertainty in the energy value. On average, the magnitude of such uncertainty will be determined by the level of "noise" in the environment. When the probe particle approaches the power center at a distance less than r_{min} , the particle will already begin to feel the predominant influence of the stationary field φ , which at some distance will significantly exceed the level of stochastic noise. At distances $r < r_{min}$, pair interaction of particles begins.

So, a probe particle with any energy received from the source before entering into interaction with the stationary field of the center inside the space $r < r_{min}$ already has an indeterminate energy at the level of stochastic noise of the medium. And the second important circumstance (important for the case of describing the interaction by methods of the theory of integers) is that in this case, the average value of the noise energy at the moment the particle appears at the point r_{min} can be taken as the unit of measure of the energy of the probe particle. For the averaging time, we can take the time of flight of the particle from the point r_A to the point r_{min} . With an increase in the level of stochastic noise at the place of the experiment (for example, with an artificial increase with the help of noise sources), the number of units of measure (that is, the number that expresses the initial energy of the probe particle) for a given even large energy of the probe particle can be made quite small, such, that the square of units of measure will not have decomposins into three other squares and then the probe particle must pass through the power center without interacting with it (if a probe particle is a carrier of electric current, then at a certain noise level it does not dissipate on power centers, which means that the phenomenon of superconductivity should be observed - we have such an unexpected application of a physical result to technology).

It is clear from the above scheme of the experiment that if particles with exactly the same energy are emitted from the source of probe particles all the time, then at the point r_{min} for each new particle, the energy value may differ from the previous value by the value of the double amplitude of one of the variable components of the environmental noise, at the moment when the particle reaches the point r_{min} . Then the number of units of measure of energy for such two particles will also differ, and the results of scattering for two particles (for two different squares of the numbers of units of measure) will also differ somewhat. As a result, for many particles we will obtain a probability distribution of scattering points on the sphere, despite the fact that the particles follow one another with energy with its strict value at the moment of departure from the point r_A . In addition to changing the energy value for particles, the result of scattering will also be affected by stochastic fields during the passage of a particle in the zone of influence of the stationary field of the scattering center (in the zone of pair interaction). The influence of stochastic fields at this time will be especially significant if the absolute value of the energy of the probe particle is small, and the particle will stay in the interaction zone for a long time.

Thus, the physical nature of the indeterministic behavior of interacting quantum physical objects in the already established world becomes clear, as well as the nature of the obligatory probabilistic state of a particle *before it enters into a pair interaction*. In this case, no measurement of the state of the particle before its entry into the interaction occurs. It is also clear that practically all interactions in nature occur without the participation of an observer (a person with instruments). And there is no doubt that such interactions *also have a probabilistic character*, regardless of whether we describe them by the methods of quantum mechanics or not.

It should be noted separately that the scattering problem can be solved by methods of integer theory for an arbitrary distribution of the scattering potential by modeling such a potential using steps from δ -functions.

4. Conclusion

The materials presented in the article suggest that the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities is the basis of Bohr's quantum hypothesis. The units of measure of the conserved quantities for the bound states of the electron in an atom are their values for the ground state. This creates a clear cause-and-effect relationship between all conceivable "allowed" states of the atomic system, that is it can be argued that any state of an electron in an atom is strictly determined.

The study of the scattering of free electrons by a power center with a distributed potential leads to the conclusion that the unit of measure of energy for them in a real experiment can be the average level of "energy noise" of the environment in which the experiment is carried out. The uncertainty of the energy of a probe particle *that enters into interaction* will be determined by the level of stochastic noise of the medium where the experiment is carried out. Such uncertainty of the state of a particle *before it enters into a pair interaction* is fundamentally irremovable, because the interaction

is carried out in the World that has already taken place. *Thus, one can understand the true physical reason for the phenomenon of indeterminism in the interaction of physical objects of the microworld.*

When scattering on a force center of probe particles with a fixed unit of measure, quantization is observed in the scattering angles, especially in the region of large deflection angles. When the absolute value of the energy of the probe particles decreases, the number of its scatterings will decrease. At some point, the square of the units of measure will not have factorizations into three other squares, which means that *the particle will pass by the scattering center without scattering at this energy.*

The principle of commensurability of conserved quantities has a universal character and asserts that *any new states of physically interacting systems are realized in Nature only when the conditions of commensurability are met for all conserved quantities that are relevant to this interaction.*

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